

THE PROCESS OF FORMING RESEARCH SKILLS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Annotation: modern society, in which the current science technology has developed, sets itself the task of training personnel who are independent thinkers, have their own word, have a scientific creative approach, are mobile, organizers, innovators, able to connect the knowledge they receive with life. The article provides feedback on the tasks of the teacher in directing students to research activities from the primary school period, the content and requirements of modern education, the formation of research skills.

Keywords: stages of research, cognitive activity, interaction, development of research activities...

In connection with the solution of modern educational problems, teachers are looking for content, new forms, methods, teaching tools that create practically wide opportunities for self-expression, self-development and self-realization of the personality of students.

The introduction of international assessment research into the educational system of our republic, the formation of students' research activities are used to various degrees in the practice of schools.

The formation of research activities is carried out in part within the framework of educational programs that develop for primary schools. The idea of developing education was put forward in the early 20th century. famous Russian psychologist L.S. Vygotsky. He substantiated the position of the leading development of learning ahead of development and behind it. The most common programs for the development of education in modern schools are L.V. Zankova, D.B. Elkonin-V.V.

Davydov, " School 2000"(E.V. and R.N.Buneevs), Vakhrushev, A.A. Leontiev et al), " School 2100 ..."(L. G. Peterson). In the programs and concepts of courses, methodological developments, it is emphasized that in order to achieve the goal of the maximum development of the child, it is necessary to build the course of the lesson in the form of the search for new knowledge, that is, it is emphasized that the orientation of students to research should be carried out through problematic,

L.Zankov talks about creating conditions in the classroom for the manifestation of the student's independent cognitive activity, saying that each task should stimulate mental actions, stimulate observation, comparison, clarify patterns, draw conclusions, include autonomy and creativity to carry out collective and individual research.

D.B.Elkonin-V.V.In Davydov's proposed system, research activities occupy one of the most important places in educational activities. In this, the reader is seen as an independent manager of all processes: setting a goal, planning, carrying out work, analyzing the result. The positions mentioned are the basis for the formation of research activities in students.

The main task of the teacher is not only to inform the conclusions of the subject, but also to guide students to research activities. The relevance of involving students in research activities and the formation of research skills is conditioned by the following:

- the fact that modern education is aimed at the formation of a personality with such qualities as Independence, activity, creative approach to solving emerging problems;
- the formation of research skills it is important to start with a small school age period, since during this period many personal qualities appear on which the future success of a person depends. R & D activities are a natural need for a young child, for its implementation it is enough to equip him with the necessary skills.
- at a young age, it is easiest to include a child in the active process of learning the world, himself and the world itself. The development of cognitive interest and

willingness to discover new things necessitates the development of independence and activity in the process of cognition. And independence from internal motivation forms the need to approach any scientific or life problem from a research, creative position.

It is a research activity to determine the essence of phenomena and processes based on the collaborative activities of the student and teacher.

The aim of the partnership is to create conditions for research activities and to form research skills to develop the research skills of younger students. In order to effectively implement this goal, it is necessary to carry out several tasks:

- analysis and study of methodological and psychological and pedagogical literature on this topic;
- to involve young schoolchildren in independent research activities, the creative process, to form an interest in exploring the world and discovering a new one, to attract children to search and work with various resources and tools;
- development of children's research, creative and research activity.

The development of research skills in elementary students is carried out in 4 stages, which corresponds to 4 years of study in elementary school.1-bosqich:

1st Class A.I.Savenkov believes that the development of research skills should be started with teaching, the propaedeutics of conducting scientific research work in subsequent classes.

In the 1st grade, it is possible to include in the classroom tasks aimed at analysis, synthesis, classification, comparison, generalization. To activate the cognitive research activities of students, it is recommended to use: riddles, puzzles, charades, joke tasks, tasks for the development of logical tasks and creative abilities; game moments associated with the inclusion of fairy-tale characters in the course of the lesson (helping to ask questions, learn, review, check, describe, etc.).

Stage 2 Class 2 operates the following routes:

1. Acquaintance with theoretical concepts of Research Activity: Research, problem, purpose, tasks, hypothesis, methods.

2. According to a clear plan (subject to all stages), the implementation of collective research on various topics.

3. In various classes, work with problematic and research methods, dictionaries and other sources of information is used.

4. The lesson offers tasks aimed at determining the various properties and actions of objects, their variety, constructing a sequence of actions; comparing the set of objects and objects, logical tasks are offered. Surveillance training continues.

Stage 3-3rd grade:

1. Students will continue to be familiar with research theory.

2. A collective study is carried out on the given topic.

3. Students conduct independent short-term research work using existing knowledge and skills.

Stage 4-4th grade:

1. With the source of Information, great attention is paid to the ability to work with the information itself, process texts, present the result of its work in the form of a text, diagram, model.

2. The preparation and conduct of independent long-term research work on topics of interest to students is carried out.

To develop students ' research skills, the teacher must create conditions that meet the goal. In the methodology of primary education, the following stand out:

1. Purposefulness and consistency. Work on the development of research skills should be carried out both in the classroom and in extracurricular activities.

2. Motivation. In order for students to realize their talent, abilities and capabilities, they need to see the content of their creative independent activity.

3. Taking into account age characteristics. Research can be carried out, it should be interesting, interesting and useful. All stages of research work should be built at a convenient level for a smaller student.

4. Psychological comfort. The teacher should give each child the opportunity to trust himself, show himself from the best side, support, help, encourage if something does not work out.

5. The personality of the teacher. In order for research work to be effective, a creative, new, advanced aspiring higher education teacher is needed in his work.

6. Creative environment. The teacher contributes to the creation of a creative, working environment.

Directing students to research activities and instilling a spirit of research in the content of the Sciences aims to provide the following aspects:

- The ability to master research methods and their use in the study of topics of any subjects of the school course;

- The possibility of developing interests in certain school subjects and the process of knowing the world around them and reality in general;

- The ability to apply the acquired knowledge and skills in the implementation of their ideas and interests.

When organizing educational activities, the teacher must work on the formation of the following skills:

1. Be able to organize your own work (Organization of the workplace, planning the work).

2. Skills and knowledge of a research nature (choosing a research topic, planning stages of research, searching for information, choosing methods for solving a problem).

3. The ability to work with information sources (Internet, dictionaries, encyclopedias, scientific articles, children's newspapers and magazines, school textbooks, TV Shows, Movies and cartoons, etc.).
4. The ability to present your own results creative work to fulfill the requirements for the speaker's speech, competently build speech, design works (projects) in manual, printed, electronic, artistic or other versions).

Elementary level research activities can be designed by the teacher at a certain stage of the lesson, episodic or fragmented, for the entire lesson, or for long-term research using existing knowledge and skills.

In the process of carrying out research based on clearly developed plans, children develop theoretical knowledge and practical skills.

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